

Oral Presentation #48 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The gastrointestinal system is one of the most frequently infected parts of the human body. Parasitic infections represent a significant public health issue, particularly in developing countries (Haque et al., 2003). These parasites, which are transmitted through water and food, can cause a range of clinical presentations from mild gastrointestinal disorders to serious systemic complications. Researchers have reported that *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Giardia intestinalis*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Ascaris lumbricoides*, and *Strongyloides stercoralis* are among the most commonly encountered gastrointestinal parasites worldwide (WHO, 2020). Accurate diagnosis of these infections is crucial for both effective individual treatment and public health management. Laboratory diagnostic methods are an essential part of clinical practice (Garcia, 2007). Various laboratory techniques, including stool microscopy, antigen detection tests, molecular methods (PCR), serological tests, and culture, are used to diagnose parasitic infections. Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of sensitivity, specificity, ease of application, and cost (Ryan & Caccio, 2013). This study aims to discuss in detail the main methods used in the laboratory diagnosis of gastrointestinal parasitic infections, evaluate the effectiveness, areas of use, and recent developments in each method.

Materials and Methods: In this study, frequently used diagnostic methods were reviewed and compared based on source information.

Results: Gastrointestinal parasites are diagnosed through stool microscopy, direct examination, concentration methods, antigen detection tests, serological tests, and culture methods.

Conclusion: The laboratory methods discussed in this study have various advantages and disadvantages in terms of diagnostic accuracy, applicability, cost, and time. While classical microscopic methods are still the most widely used diagnostic tools, they may not always be sufficient due to their low sensitivity and observer dependency. In such cases, antigen tests and molecular methods offer higher accuracy in parasite detection. Molecular methods (PCR, Real-Time PCR) are particularly valuable as they enable species-level diagnosis and can yield positive results even in low-intensity infections. However, the widespread use of these methods is still limited due to costs, infrastructure requirements, and the need for specialized personnel. This limitation is especially significant in resource-limited regions. It is recommended that current molecular and antigen-based methods should be more widely used in diagnosing parasitic infections. A combination of multiple methods should be incorporated into diagnostic algorithms, healthcare professionals should receive training on these methods, and public health campaigns should be initiated to raise awareness.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Laboratory methods, parasitic infections, gastrointestinal system

INTRODUCTION

The gastrointestinal system is one of the most commonly infected regions of the human body. Parasitic infections, particularly in developing countries, represent a major public health concern (Haque et al., 2003). These parasites, transmitted through contaminated water and food, can cause a wide spectrum of clinical symptoms, ranging from mild gastrointestinal discomfort to severe systemic complications. Researchers have identified *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Giardia intestinalis*, *Cryptosporidium* spp., *Ascaris lumbricoides*, and *Strongyloides stercoralis* as some of the most common gastrointestinal parasites worldwide (WHO, 2020). Accurate diagnosis of these infections is critical for both individual treatment success and public health. In this regard, laboratory diagnostic methods are an essential part of the clinical approach (Garcia, 2007). Techniques such as stool microscopy, antigen detection tests, molecular methods (PCR), serological tests, and culture are utilized for the identification of parasitic agents. Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of sensitivity, specificity, ease of application, and cost (Ryan & Caccio, 2013). This study comprehensively reviews the main diagnostic methods used in the detection of gastrointestinal parasitic infections, evaluating the effectiveness, applications, and recent developments of each method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The commonly used diagnostic methods were researched from literature sources and comparatively evaluated.

RESULTS

Parasitic diagnosis is carried out using methods such as direct stool microscopy and concentration techniques, antigen detection tests, serological tests, and culture methods (Table 1).

Table 1
Comparison of Diagnostic Methods

Method	Sensitivity	Specificity	Speed	Cost	Application Area
Microscopy	Moderate	Moderate	Medium	Low	All parasites
Antigen Tests	High	High	Fast	Moderate	<i>Giardia</i> , <i>Cryptosporidium</i>
PCR	Very High	Very High	Medium	High	Species/subtype ID, mixed infections
Serology	Moderate-High	Moderate	Medium	Moderate	Systemic/invasive parasites
Culture	Low	High	Slow	Moderate-High	Research purposes, some amoeba species

CONCLUSION

The laboratory methods discussed in this study have various advantages and disadvantages in terms of diagnostic accuracy, feasibility, cost, and time. Although classical microscopic methods are still the most commonly used diagnostic tools, they may not always be sufficient alone due to their lower sensitivity and reliance on the observer. In such cases, antigen detection and molecular methods provide higher diagnostic accuracy.

Molecular methods (PCR, Real-Time PCR) allow for species-level diagnosis and can detect even low-intensity infections, making them particularly valuable. However, their widespread use remains limited due to cost, infrastructure, and the need for skilled personnel -factors that present significant barriers, especially in resource- limited settings.

The study emphasizes the need for:

- wider use of updated molecular and antigen-based methods,
- integration of combined diagnostic algorithms,
- training of healthcare personnel in these techniques,
- and public awareness campaigns to increase community knowledge.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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